

A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE IMPACT OF SECONDARY SCHOOLS ORIENTATION PROGRAMMES DYNAMICS ON STUDENTS' SCHOOL CONNECTEDNESS IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KENYA

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Abstract:

Cases of student's unrest are on the rise despite the spirited effort by the education stakeholders to curtail them. They have recently taken a violent dimension, leading damage of property and even loss of life during fires in school. This is an indicator of a relationship gone sour right from orientation, where the learners neither connect nor associate themselves with the school community, facilities and the programmes offered. The researchers used critical analysis research methodology to critically analyse the impact of secondary schools orientation programmes dynamics on the student's school connectedness in secondary schools in Kenya. Using this method, the researchers assessed the various orientation programmes dynamics and how they impact on the students' school connectedness against the backdrop of the induction programmes currently undertaken in secondary schools. The study found out that the orientation programmes offered in secondary schools exclude key stake holders, facilities and educational programmes. They also lack support mechanisms to sustain the momentum of the orientation week. Further, they run in the same way over time and hardly involve any feedback or evaluation processes. The study concluded that secondary schools recognise the importance and carry out a form of orientation for new students. These induction programmes achieve the intended short term goals but lack sustainability. Among the recommendations made is that school administrations should have

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orientation programmes which include parents and school community, allow feedback and equate the process. The ministry of education should also do budgetary allocations that would cater for orientation programmes and capacity building in schools. This would facilitate funding of more comprehensive and sustainable orientation programmes, which would in turn raise the level of school connectedness.

Keywords: orientation programme, feedback, evaluation, support systems

1. Introduction

The tail of a lizard is all that it has. The tails plays a vital role in optimal performance for key functions such as jumping, running, balancing and masquerading. If a lizard has nothing to wag, it becomes difficult to feed, escape from its prey and even reproduce! This is a perfect example of learners without school connectedness to the institution which forms part of whom and what the students are. From schools, students are expected to acquire not only academic grades but also key values such as responsibility. In Kenya, despite the high teacher-student ratio in pre-primary and lower primary levels, the learners are attached to the same teacher, who plays a great role in inducting the new learner into the school (Dodge & Colker, 1992). At universities, new students are admitted about a week before the arrival of the continuing students. This allows the university administration to execute an orientation programme for the newly admitted cohort. The researchers sought to critique the impact of orientation programmes dynamics on school connectedness in secondary schools in Kenya.

2. Statement of the problem

Kenya and the world at large, has experienced outrageous antisocial behaviours exhibited by secondary school students. In Kenya there have been frequent unrests in schools where bullying and destruction of school property have been witnessed. Cases of alumni who deliberately refuse to clear school fees in their previous institutions are also rampant. Many times students transfer to new schools with very little or no information shared with about their past. Orientation programme structure for such learners ought to be differently constructed due to the potential risks of vices infiltrating into a school through such learners. The programme also needs to take care of the dissident or traumatised incoming learners who may only identified after causing

trouble, if no information is shared. Feedback and evaluation play a key role in focusing and improving programme structures and delivery methods.

Despite the many attempts made by schools administrator to orientate learners every year, instances of non-existing or non-functional alumni associations are on the rise, with the current learners in schools destroying property and even setting schools on fire at the slightest provocation. This raises a question of learners' connectedness to their institutions and at which point it was lost. The researchers therefore set out to analyse the impact of orientation programmes dynamics on school connectedness.

3. Purpose of the study

The researchers carried out this study with the purpose to analyse critically the impact of orientation programmes dynamics on students' school connectedness in secondary schools. This was guided by the objectives focusing on the impact of awareness and insight into facilities provided by a school, human resource, school culture, co-curriculum activities and academic expectations of the learner.

4. Research objectives

1. To analyse critically the impact of Orientation information sharing on school connectedness in secondary schools in Kenya.
2. To analyse critically the impact of the orientation program structure and inclusiveness on school connectedness.
3. To critically analyse the impact of the orientation program Feedback on school connectedness.
4. To critically analyse the impact of the orientation programme Support on school connectedness.
5. To critically analyse the impact of the orientation programme evaluation on school connectedness.

5. Research questions

1. What is the impact of orientation information sharing on schools on connectedness?
2. How does orientation program structure and inclusiveness impacts on school connectedness?

3. To what extent does the orientation program Feedback impact on school connectedness?
4. What is the impact of orientation programme Support on school connectedness?
5. How does orientation programme evaluation impact on school connectedness?

6. Significance of the study

This study may benefit the Ministry of Education because it may inform on how policies impact on school connectedness. The findings may also inform schools principals and the schools' on the importance of orientation information sharing and its impact on school connectedness. Teachers who are key stakeholders in planning secondary schools orientation programmes and students are the main carriers of school culture. The research findings may inform them about the impact of school culture, on connectedness.

7. Critical review

7.1 Impact of Orientation information sharing on school connectedness

The learners and information about them should transit together. There is need for an information sharing session between the teachers, administration, parents and the learner at the beginning of the transition. The orientation programmes need to share enough details about available facilities and culture. Where these details are omitted, one party may come to learn later of the undesirable vices, practices and culture, resulting to serious mistrust issues which negatively impact on school connectedness. (Duggins, 2016). It is therefore difficult to induct the new students in an individualised manner if parents do not share enough information with the school regarding their children.

In Finland - one of the finest education systems in the world - the nine years of free compulsory education starting at age seven. At each transition, actual records of the transiting learners are shared by the parents with the new school (Duggins, 2016). This is unlike what happens in many secondary schools in Kenya that do orientation of the new students, where little or no information is shared. This holding of information about the learner sheds a cloud of uncertainty among the two parties due to the fear of unknown. Information about an institution should be available to the participants of an orientation programme promptly and in details. This may be done through websites where updates can be regularly done or by internal developed and circulated soft copies of key information (Duggins, 2016).

7.2 Critical analysis of the impact of orientation programme structure and inclusiveness on school connectedness

Structuring of orientation programme greatly influences how it appeals to the subjects. It also determines how well the implementers of the programme understand and execute the procedural steps in the programme. There also needs to be a smooth flow of ideas and activities that are laid down in the orientation programme, this closes a lot of communication gaps between the hosts and visitors.

Time allocated to the various components of an orientation programme communicates volume on the importance of the item or the person allocated to that particular time. The timing of the reporting dates of the new students in a learning institution determines the amount of attention given to the new students, how thorough and the level of access and interaction the learners have with both the personnel and facilities. Students joining secondary schools at form one in Kenya, report after the continuing students. They therefore find an already congested school environment. A congested environment during orientation period might lead to development of a feeling of harassment and result to lack of ownership of the process. Lack of ownership of this process becomes step towards a weak cord between the learner and the new institution.

An effective orientation programme is an amalgamation of both indoor and outdoor activities. The audience needs to be well engaged in activities in order for them to remain alert. The activities should be well chosen to include such components as energizers and team building activities. Modern and effective orientation programmes are those that meet the needs of the new students. This is done by including some topics of interest to both students and parents, such as financial aid and literacy. Schools admit students from varied backgrounds. While some students may be economically endowed, others may be managing the largest amount of money ever; the pocket money. Some parents too would benefit with information on how to fund education.

An orientation programme should be an inclusive process. The host community consisting of continuing students, teaching and non-teaching staff need to be active participants. Orientation sessions are opportune times for parents to internalise where they are leaving their children and in whose hands. A school tour of the key premises and an explanation of opportunities in these facilities go a long way in creating a bond between the new students and the school. This brings the stakeholders on board in enhancing school connectedness.

A typical scenario currently is that of an arrangement of tables near the school gate on the reporting day. Most parents do not get to tour the school on the reporting day. The form one students are normally left in the hands of strangers in a strange

environment. Research indicate that in an environment where bullying occurs, incidents occurring in the first few days go unreported. This might be a prevalent problem in schools where no thorough orientation is done hence completely hinder school connectedness (Sandhu, 2016).

7.3 Critical analysis of the impact of orientation programme feedback on school connectedness

Feedback is a report on the progress in a process geared towards achieving a target. This is a vital instrument for providing specific performance pointers and giving corrective guidance for an ongoing process (Hattie, 2012). Orientation of new learners in an institution is the first attempt of the welcoming community to help the incoming learner develop school connectedness. It is therefore important to get immediate feedback on the process progress (Branford, Brown, & Cooking, 2000). This is a vital instrument for assessing and guiding the path that performance is taking.

When done constructively, feedback is a benefit to both the orientation programme facilitators as well as the participants. Through a prompt feedback system, facilitators learn the participants better, create a rapport with them and get an opportunity to use the feedback to focus on the key areas of the proceedings. Participant of an orientation programme are able to freely identify with the facilitators, air their areas of need and own up the process.

It can therefore be said that an orientation programme is not a sitting session in which the facilitators possess and disseminate the information while the participants are the passive recipients. This is largely what happens in many secondary schools and unless the stakeholders and facilitators modernise their orientation programmes to include feedback, the current gaps and disconnects, the relevance of their programmes will continue dwindling.

7.4 Critical analysis of the impact of orientation programme Support on school connectedness

All that there is in a school cannot be explained in a day or a week. It is therefore fundamental for a school to set up support systems that will build on the orientation programme. Orientation is not an event, it is a process. A fresh student's first day or week orientation is the beginning and not the end of the orientation process.

A school is a dynamic institution that responds to the ever growing societal needs, technology and shifts in global development goals. Each time the school undertakes restructuring in terms of facilities, human resource or school programmes, its community needs to undergo a formal orientation in order to own up the change.

There also exist a number of options that may be used as orientation process supports systems. 'Buddy' system is one such system, where a new student is paired with a continuing student. In this situation, the continuing student is the carrier of the deep rooted school values and culture, and passes them via association to the new learner. Mentorship is another system in which a continuing student is carefully selected to pass the school's core values and culture to a small group of new students. Some institutions take it a notch higher and include an adult in the mentorship group, hence call them family systems. The adult provides guidance on all issues surrounding the members of their group. This form of orientation ensures that the new and continuing learners acquire continuous orientation which enhances school connectedness and reduces the risk of emergence of aggressive behaviors among the youth (Duggins et al, 2016)

Team building enables the participants to achieve both organisational and personal goals. (Mbirua, Thinguri, 2016). Regular capacity building sessions serve well for re-orientation of the school community. They form useful for activating or activating core values and culture. Such activities help in integrating members of the school community, boosting cohesion and school connectedness. Should differences arise in school, skills obtained during team building sessions come in handy in exercising dialogue.

Ongoing orientation can also be done through online systems. Maps, simulations and customised software are key in introduction of facilities, their location in the school compound as well as library procedures. This does not have to happen on the first day in school. They are support systems that the learners can independently use and acquire more detailed and accurate information that other people would avail.

7.5 Critical analysis of the impact of orientation programme evaluation on school connectedness

Key aspects of a programme need to be examined and rated. This enables the evaluator to know how much value something has and is based on criteria that has been defined. This would be a very instrumental exercise for an orientation programme. Evaluation would inform on the effectiveness and efficiency of the orientation process (Hattie, 2012). There are cases where such a programme delivers below expectations or even delivers nothing at all. At times, results are got but at a very high cost.

Evaluation would help the facilitators of an orientation programme and stakeholders in a school to identify errors that keep recurring. This is an important step in making the process meaningful and successful. Non-functioning and untenable components of the programme are identified, restructured or even omitted in future

programmes. Components that would raise the level of school connectedness are also suggested during the evaluation exercise.

Evaluation is based on feedback. If constructive feedback is taken positively and used well in the evaluation process, it has ability to make orientation process a powerful tool for enhancing school connectedness (Hattie, 2012).

8. Research methodology

In this research, qualitative with critical analysis were used as the research methodologies. This method allows the researchers to dig into a wide range of data within a short time and at a low cost (Gatara, 2010). It enabled the researchers critique the impact of orientation programmes on school connectedness and come up with research findings. The research also gave recommendations on how orientation programmes can be improved to enhance school connectedness.

9. Research findings

A well thought out orientation programme plays a vital role in raising the level of school connectedness. It is the first attempt to bond a new group with the institution's facilities, programmes as well as the human resource. It therefore needs to be well outlined, organised and timelines in it followed. An orientation programme should be all inclusive. It should not leave out any of the facilities in the compound, a programme offered by the institution or even key procedures undertaken by the school community. It should also include all the school's stake holders such as students, teachers, non-teaching staff as well as the parents. A good orientation process should have feedback mechanisms, where constructive feedback can be given. It also provides room for appreciation and taking action on the feedback.

A successful orientation requires support systems which would introduce and guide the learners on the components of the programme that may not be learnt over a short period. These support systems are also pivotal in cementing the gains made by the orientation programme. Evaluation of the orientation programmes is hardly done in secondary schools. This results to recycling of the errors made in the initial programmes. It further leads to orientation programmes that do not address the needs of a 21st century learner, a factor the highly hinders school connectedness.

10. Recommendations

The researchers drew the following recommendations from the study:

1. Secondary school should prepare all inclusive orientation program that brings all stakeholders on board.
2. Orientation programme facilitators should allow time for constructive feedback and act on it to improve the process.
3. Creative and interesting methods that involve outdoor activities and use of technology should be used to deliver the content of an orientation programme. Innovations as online activities and simulations could be used to deliver a lot within a short time and in an interesting way.
4. School administrators should put in place orientation programme support systems that would consolidate the gains made during the first day or week induction programme.
5. Education stakeholders in schools should evaluate their orientation programmes in order to keep them modern and relevant to the recipients.
6. When funding secondary schools, the ministry of education should include a vote head that can facilitate orientation programmes and capacity building in schools.

11. Conclusions

Orientation programmes for new secondary school students hardly happens. When they do, they are normally boring, shallow, inadequate and not focused. The sessions still take place in a sitting session, involve just a few teachers and done in the same way year in year out. They hardly allow time for feedback, have no support systems and are hardly evaluated. This creates disconnect between the learners on the one side, and school facilities, programmes and human resource on the other side. As a result, irritability, confrontation and aggression have become prevalent in our learning institutions. This calls for urgent intervention measures - such as the ones suggested by this study- taken by schools administration to raise school connectedness, before the situation gets completely out of hand.

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